

Supplementary Materials for Optimizing dynamic shared E-moped relocation with long-term effect via deep reinforcement learning

1. Additional data for prediction model

The built environment and weather data are collected to assist in the prediction model training based on our previous study. The built environment includes POIs, spatial relationships, and socio-demographics. To further divide into subcategories, the POI data includes recreation, public service, shop and private service, restaurant, religious, finance, education, and medical care, collected from OpenStreetMap (2022). In addition, we particularly collect other POI location data of transit (including shared bikes (Department of Information Technology, Taipei City Government, 2022b), buses (Department of Information Technology, Taipei City Government, 2022a; Transportation Department, New Taipei City Government, 2023), MRT (Ministry of Digital Affairs, Taiwan, 2017), trains (National Land Surveying and Mapping Center, Ministry of the Interior, Taiwan, 2023b), and HSR (National Land Surveying and Mapping Center, Ministry of the Interior, Taiwan, 2023a)) and school (including elementary schools, junior high schools, high schools, and colleges (Ministry of Education, Taiwan, 2023)). Regarding spatial relationships, the influential features include street density, street intersection density, and distance between each region and the city center, representing regional connectivity and accessibility. The street data collected from OpenStreetMap (2022) can all evaluate those features. Regarding socio-demographics, we collect the governmental open data from Ministry of the Interior, Taiwan (2021), including sex, age groups, and education levels. Regarding the weather data, the average temperature, precipitation, average relative humidity, and average wind speed are considered (Central Weather Bureau, Taiwan, 2021).

2. Concept of SAC

In the SAC model, the objective function $J(\pi)$ introduces entropy maximization to enhance policy exploration and training stability, defined as Eq. S1:

$$J(\pi) = \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \pi} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t (r(s_t, a_t) + \alpha \mathcal{H}(\pi(\cdot | s_t))) \right] \quad (\text{S1})$$

where π is the policy stochastic policy parameterized by ϕ which defines the probability of taking action a_t given state s_t . τ is a trajectory $(s_0, a_0, s_1, a_1, \dots)$ generated by π . $r(s_t, a_t)$ represents the reward function, providing a scalar feedback signal at each step t . The discount factor $\gamma \in (0, 1]$ is used to discount the impact of future rewards relative to immediate rewards. α represents the temperature parameter, controlling the balance between reward and entropy maximization. $\mathcal{H}(\pi(\cdot | s_t))$ is the entropy of the policy, defined as Eq. S2:

$$\mathcal{H}(\pi(\cdot | s_t)) = -\mathbb{E}_{a_t \sim \pi} [\log \pi(a_t | s_t)] \quad (\text{S2})$$

To optimize this objective, the SAC maintains separate function approximators for the policy $\pi_\phi(a_t | s_t)$ and the soft Q-function $Q_\theta(s_t, a_t)$. The model aims to maximize both the expected Q-value and the entropy of the policy distribution. The policy loss is defined as Eq. S3:

$$\mathcal{L}_\pi(\phi) = \mathbb{E}_{s_t \sim \mathcal{D}, a_t \sim \pi_\phi} [\alpha \log \pi_\phi(a_t | s_t) - Q_\theta(s_t, a_t)] \quad (\text{S3})$$

where \mathcal{D} is the experience replay buffer. The critic model is trained to minimize the temporal-difference (TD) error between its Q-value predictions and a soft Bellman backup. The critic loss is defined as Eq. S4:

$$\mathcal{L}_Q(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_{(s_t, a_t) \sim \mathcal{D}} \left[(Q_\theta(s_t, a_t) - y_t)^2 \right] \quad (\text{S4})$$

where the soft TD target y_t is computed as:

$$y_t = r_t + \gamma \mathbb{E}_{a_{t+1} \sim \pi_\phi} \left[\min_{i=1,2} Q_{\bar{\theta}_i}(s_{t+1}, a_{t+1}) - \alpha \log \pi_\phi(a_{t+1} | s_{t+1}) \right] \quad (\text{S5})$$

This equation employs two Q-networks $Q_{\theta_1}, Q_{\theta_2}$ and their corresponding target networks $Q_{\bar{\theta}_1}, Q_{\bar{\theta}_2}$ to reduce overestimation bias Haarnoja et al. (2018). The target networks are updated using a soft update scheme to improve training stability.

3. Action-constrained approach

Based on our definitions of action-constrained conditions in Section 3.4, they can be incorporated from Algorithm 1 to Algorithm 4:

Algorithm 1: Constraint on traversed regions

Input: $a \in \mathbb{Z}^{n_{truck} \times n_{region}}$

Output: $a^{c1} \in \mathbb{Z}^{n_{truck} \times n_{region}}$

```

1 foreach  $j \in J_{truck}$  do
2   foreach  $i \in I_{region}$  do
3     if  $i \in I_{region}^{\max} \cup I_{region}^{\min}$  then
4        $a_{j,i}^{c1} \leftarrow a_{j,i};$ 
5     else
6        $a_{j,i}^{c1} \leftarrow 0;$ 

```

Algorithm 2: Constraint by loading capacity

Input: $a^{c1} \in \mathbb{Z}^{n_{truck} \times n_{region}}, c_{load}$ **Output:** $a^{c2} \in \mathbb{Z}^{n_{truck} \times n_{region}}$

```
1 foreach  $j \in J_{truck}$  do
2   | foreach  $i \in I_{region}$  do
3     | if  $a_{j,i}^{c1} > c_{load}$  then
4       |    $a_{j,i}^{c2} \leftarrow c_{load}$ ;
5     | else
6       |   if  $a_{j,i}^{c1} < -c_{load}$  then
7         |      $a_{j,i}^{c2} \leftarrow -c_{load}$ ;
8       |   else
9         |      $a_{j,i}^{c2} \leftarrow a_{j,i}^{c1}$ ;
```

Algorithm 3: Constraint by E-moped availability

Input: $a^{c2} \in \mathbb{Z}^{n_{truck} \times n_{region}}, n^{avail} \in \mathbb{Z}^{n_{region}}$ **Output:** a^{c3}

```
1 foreach  $j \in J_{truck}$  do
2   | foreach  $i \in I_{region}$  do
3     | if  $a_{j,i}^{c2} < 0 \wedge -a_{j,i}^{c2} > n_i^{avail}$  then
4       |    $a_{j,i}^{c3} \leftarrow -n_i^{avail}$ ;
5     | else
6       |    $a_{j,i}^{c3} \leftarrow a_{j,i}^{c2}$ ;
```

where a represents the suggested action output by the policy model (with the period index t omitted for brevity). a^{c1} , a^{c2} , a^{c3} , and a^c represent the constrained action after the processes of Algorithm 1, Algorithm 2, Algorithm 3, and Algorithm 4, respectively. Algorithm 4 is a simplified approach to ensure each truck's action inner-balance during a route. Without violating Algorithm 1, Algorithm 2, and Algorithm 3, the adjustment in Row 1 to 20 is performed by amplifying the existing non-zero action elements to achieve balance (i.e., making the balance value $b_j = 0$). If balance cannot be achieved through this process, the adjustment in Row 21 to 33 instead reduces the existing non-zero action elements to reach balance (with the worst case resulting in an action of $\{0\}$).

Algorithm 4: Constraint for inner-balance

Input: a^{c3}, n^{avail} **Output:** a^c

```
1 foreach  $j \in J_{truck}$  do
2    $\mathbf{a}_j \leftarrow$  row  $j$  of  $a^{c3}$ ; balance value  $b_j \leftarrow \sum_i \mathbf{a}_j[i]$ ;
3   if  $b_j < 0$  then
4     candidate list  $C \leftarrow \{i \mid \mathbf{a}_j[i] > 0\}$ ; while  $b_j < 0 \wedge C \neq \emptyset$  do
5       Randomly pick  $i \in C$ ;
6       if  $\mathbf{a}_j[i] < c_{load}$  then
7          $\mathbf{a}_j[i] \leftarrow \mathbf{a}_j[i] + 1$ ;  $b_j \leftarrow b_j + 1$ ;
8         if  $\mathbf{a}_j[i] = c_{load}$  then
9           remove  $i$  from  $C$ ;
10      else
11        remove  $i$  from  $C$ ;
12  else if  $b_j > 0$  then
13    candidate list  $C \leftarrow \{i \mid \mathbf{a}_j[i] < 0\}$ ; while  $b_j > 0 \wedge C \neq \emptyset$  do
14      Randomly pick  $i \in C$ ;
15      if  $\mathbf{a}_j[i] > -\min(c_{load}, n^{avail}[i])$  then
16         $\mathbf{a}_j[i] \leftarrow \mathbf{a}_j[i] - 1$ ;  $b_j \leftarrow b_j - 1$ ;
17        if  $\mathbf{a}_j[i] = -\min(c_{load}, n^{avail}[i])$  then
18          remove  $i$  from  $C$ ;
19      else
20        remove  $i$  from  $C$ ;
21   $b'_j \leftarrow \sum_i \mathbf{a}_j[i]$ ;
22  if  $b'_j < 0$  then
23    candidate list  $C \leftarrow \{i \mid \mathbf{a}_j[i] < 0\}$ ; while  $b'_j < 0 \wedge C \neq \emptyset$  do
24      Randomly pick  $i \in C$ ;
25       $\mathbf{a}_j[i] \leftarrow \mathbf{a}_j[i] + 1$ ;  $b'_j \leftarrow b'_j + 1$ ;
26      if  $\mathbf{a}_j[i] = 0$  then
27        remove  $i$  from  $C$ ;
28  else if  $b'_j > 0$  then
29    candidate list  $C \leftarrow \{i \mid \mathbf{a}_j[i] > 0\}$ ; while  $b'_j > 0 \wedge C \neq \emptyset$  do
30      Randomly pick  $i \in C$ ;
31       $\mathbf{a}_j[i] \leftarrow \mathbf{a}_j[i] - 1$ ;  $b'_j \leftarrow b'_j - 1$ ;
32      if  $\mathbf{a}_j[i] = 0$  then
33        remove  $i$  from  $C$ ;
34  Assign  $\mathbf{a}_j$  as row  $j$  of  $a^c$ ;
```

4. Routing Algorithm

We consider the routing algorithm to evaluate the truck's delivery distance and prevent overestimating performance. For instance, if the suggested action for a truck is (6, -7, +8, +7, +5, -7, -7, -5), and satisfies all the above constraints. After considering the practical delivery routes and truck capacity, the feasible action can no longer fully align with the suggestion, resulting in a reduction of the performance $r_{i,t}$ by 1. The action can be revised as (5, -6, +8, +7, +5, -7, -7, -5). Despite the advantage of using a routing algorithm, solving it with linear programming at each step would significantly increase training time. Therefore, we propose adopting a transfer learning approach, incorporating the routing algorithm only in the later training episodes. The details of the training process and results are depicted in the performance results. We define the problems below to solve each truck's routing algorithm. Let $\mathbf{A} = \{(m, n) | m, n \in \mathbf{I}_{region}, m \neq n\}$ be the set of arcs between two regions. $x_{mn} \in \{0, 1\}$ ($\forall (m, n) \in \mathbf{A}$) represent a decision variable whether a truck travels from region m to region n or not. It is assumed that each truck always starts its route at the same depot station, i.e., $m = 0$. For the truck j during period t , given a prior constrained action $a_{j,t}^c \in \mathbb{Z}^{n_{region}}$, let action $a_{j,t}^r \in \mathbb{Z}^{n_{region}}$ be a modified action after the routing algorithm is solved. $a_m^c \in a_{j,t}^c$ and $a_m^r \in a_{j,t}^r$ represent their action elements, respectively. l_{mn} represents the loading of a truck traversed the arc (m, n) . δ_{mn}^{dist} represents the street distance between two centers of region m and n . We can define hierarchical objective functions, prioritizing the maximization of the total number of E-mopeds as Eq.S6a, followed by minimizing the total travel distance of a truck as Eq.S6b:

$$\text{maximize} \quad \sum_{m \in \mathbf{I}_{region}, a_m^r > 0} a_m^r \quad (\text{S6a})$$

$$\text{minimize} \quad \sum_{(m,n) \in \mathbf{A}} x_{mn} \cdot \delta_{mn}^{dist} \quad (\text{S6b})$$

subject to:

$$x_{mn} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if the arc } (m, n) \text{ is traversed} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \forall (m, n) \in \mathbf{A} \quad (\text{S6c})$$

$$\sum_{n \in I_{region} \setminus \{0\}} x_{0n} = 1 \quad (\text{S6d})$$

$$\sum_{m \in I_{region} \setminus \{0\}} x_{m0} = \begin{cases} 1, & a_0^c > 0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (\text{S6e})$$

$$0 \leq \sum_{n \in I_{region}} x_{mn} \leq 1 \quad \forall m \in I_{region} \quad (\text{S6f})$$

$$0 \leq \sum_{m \in I_{region}} x_{mn} \leq 1 \quad \forall n \in I_{region} \quad (\text{S6g})$$

$$0 \leq \sum_{n \in I_{region}} (x_{nm} - x_{mn}) \leq 1 \quad \forall m \in I_{region} \setminus \{0\} \quad (\text{S6h})$$

$$x_{mn} + x_{nm} \leq 1 \quad \forall (m, n) \in \mathbf{A} \quad (\text{S6i})$$

$$\max(a_m^c, -c_{load}) \leq a_m^r \leq 0 \quad \forall m \in \{m \in I_{region} \mid a_m^c < 0\} \quad (\text{S6j})$$

$$0 \leq a_m^r \leq \min(a_m^c, c_{load}) \quad \forall m \in \{m \in I_{region} \mid a_m^c > 0\} \quad (\text{S6k})$$

$$a_m^r = 0 \quad \forall m \in \{m \in I_{region} \mid a_m^c = 0\} \quad (\text{S6l})$$

$$\sum_{m \in I_{region}} a_m^r = 0 \quad (\text{S6m})$$

$$\text{abs}(a_m^r) - \sum_{n \in I_{region}} x_{mn} \geq 0 \quad \forall m \in I_{region} \setminus \{0\} \quad (\text{S6n})$$

$$\sum_{n \in I_{region}} (l_{nm} - l_{mn}) = a_m^r \quad \forall m \in I_{region} \setminus \{0\} \quad (\text{S6o})$$

$$l_{mn} = 0 \quad \forall (m, n) \in \{(m, n) \in \mathbf{A} \mid x_{mn} = 0\} \quad (\text{S6p})$$

$$l_{0n} \begin{cases} = 0, & \text{if } a_0^c \geq 0 \\ \leq \min(a_0^c, c_{load}), & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \forall n \in I_{region} \setminus \{0\} \quad (\text{S6q})$$

where Eq. S6c is the definition of x_{mn} . Eq. S6d constrains each route to start at the depot ($m = 0$). Eq. S6e constrains each route not to traverse the depot again unless the depot requires a placement action. Eq. S6f constrains each region to be entered at most once. Eq. S6g constrains each region to be exited at most once. Eq. S6h requires that if a truck enters a region, it must also exit that region unless the region is the endpoint of the route. Eq. S6i prevents a truck from revisiting previously visited regions. Eq. S6j, Eq. S6k, and Eq. S6l define that route-based actions $a_{j,t}^c$ must be grounded in their corresponding actions $a_{j,t}^r$. Eq. S6m constrains the inner-balance that the total number of placement and removal should be the same. Eq. S6n requires that if a truck enters a region, a certain number of relocations must be carried out in that region. Eq. S6o defines the balance between changes in the truck's load and the number of relocations. Eq. S6p enforces that the truck's load must be zero on any arc (m, n) not traversed by a truck. Eq. S6q defines special cases of relocation occurring at the region where the depot is located. If the original relocation $a_m^c > 0$ is to place E-mopeds, the truck would initially depart from the depot with an empty load to perform tasks in other regions and return to this region at the end to complete the placement task (according to Eq. S6e). If the original relocation is to take E-mopeds, the truck would depart from the depot and collect E-mopeds in this region (with a negligible distance between the depot and this region's center) and subsequently proceed to other tasks.

5. Results of immediate reward

Moreover, we also compare the performance of each method in terms of short-term demand response, focusing solely on the immediate reward and excluding the penalty term, denoted as r_t^+ shown in Table 1. Among all methods, our approach remains the best-performing, achieving an overall average of 26.1 and a peak-period average of 79.3. In contrast, the manual relocation strategy continues to exhibit the poorest performance. The second-best performance is obtained by the C1 method, with an average of 20.6 and a peak-period average of 71.3. This result represents a

Table 1

Comparison of the model’s short-term performance in the reduction of unmet demand on the test data

Immediate positive reward r_t^+	RL method						Manual
	Ours	M1	M2	M3	C1	C2	
Average	26.1	14.9	18.0	20.1	20.6	17.8	6.4
Average during peak hours (4 p.m. – 8 p.m.)	79.3	41.3	57.7	55.0	71.3	62.0	19.3

reduction of 26.7% and 11.2% compared to ours, respectively. Among the RL-based methods, the DQN-based model (M3) exhibits the weakest performance, consistent with the results presented in the performance result. Notably, under the evaluation considering only the immediate reward, the performance of the M3 method still falls short of our proposed model, with reductions of 29.9% in the overall average and 44.2% in the peak-period average. The deficient performance of this model is likely attributable to its restricted interaction horizon, which limits the agent to a single-step transition per training sample. Although our proposed model and the M3 variant both utilize the same TD updates with one-step bootstrapped value estimates, our model considers a greater variety of state-action scenarios, which likely encourages the agent to implicitly plan for longer-term outcomes and ensures the Q-function is better trained, resulting in better policies.

6. Ablation study for the additional learning features in demand prediction

To ensure a complete and self-contained presentation of our relocation study, we summarize the prior findings (Song et al., 2025) regarding the demand prediction model integrated within our proposed RL framework. Results are based on the model trained with historical E-moped unmet demand data from Greater Taipei (April 2021). Specifically, we conducted an ablation study to compare the contributions of the proposed learning features, including the built environment, weather data (described in Section 1), and periodic features (e.g., hours, weekdays, holidays, and months). This ablation study evaluated the model’s performance by systematically removing

Table 2

Ablation study for additional learning features.

Model / feature set	MAE	MAPE ₁₀ (%)	MAPE ₄₀ (%)
Full model	3.91	31.5	26.2
w/o POI	4.82	33.1	31.1
w/o Spatial relationship	4.29	32.8	27.3
w/o Socio-demographic	4.17	32.6	30.4
w/o Periodic	4.91	37.8	39.3
w/o Weather	4.58	32.0	28.1
w/o All additions	5.47	39.4	44.6

a specific feature to determine its individual contribution (Meyes et al., 2019). The results are presented in Table 2, where the values highlighted in red indicate the worst performance for each metric, thereby representing the highest contribution of the corresponding removed feature. The most impactful feature type is the periodic features, which are evident from the highest MAE of 4.91, MAPE10 of 37.8%, and MAPE40 of 39.3%. Notably, the greater MAPE40 compared to MAPE10 suggests a heightened impact on accuracy in regions with higher demands. The second most influential features are the POI features, increasing the MAE to 4.82, MAPE10 to 33.1%, and MAPE40 to 31.1%. Weather conditions are the third influential feature, impacting the MAE with 4.58, MAPE10 with 32.0%, and MAPE40 with 28.1%. The spatial relationship and socio-demographics also contribute, with their removal leading to a deterioration in MAE to 4.29 and 4.17, respectively. Although the socio-demographic features have the slightest importance in MAE, their impact on MAPE10 is superior to weather conditions. If all additional learning features are removed, performance severely declines, with an MAE of 5.47, MAPE10 of 39.4%, and MAPE40 of 44.6%. The results generally indicate the importance of incorporating all learning features for optimal model performance. Analyzing the contribution ratio of each feature to unmet demand prediction, using MAE as an example, the ratios for POI, spatial relationship, socio-demographic, periodic, weather, and all additional features are 23.1%, 9.6%, 6.5%, 25.4%, 17%, and 39.8%, respectively.

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